

Synthesis and Characterisation of some Substituted Imidazole Adducts of Bis[(*p*-chlorophenyl)dithiophosphinato]nickel(II)

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Unlike nickel(II) dithiocarbamates with square-planar NiS_4 cores, the dithiophosphinate analogues are coordinatively unsaturated and their adducts with nitrogen and oxygen donors were reported earlier¹⁻³. However, similar adducts with biologically significant molecules such as the substituted imidazoles are not known. From the complexation point of view they are important in the sense that depending upon donor site, binding ability and steric effect, they can form a variety of complexes. Besides, 1,2-dimethylimidazole and 2-fluoromethylimidazole are reported to have weedicidal and antiviral properties^{4,5}. We report here the synthesis and characterisation of adducts of bis[(*p*-chlorophenyl)dithiophosphinato]nickel(II), $[Ni(Cltpi)_2]$ with different substituted imidazoles, i.e. 1-vinylimidazole (1-VIm), 2-methyl-1-vinylimidazole-(2-Me-1-VIm), 4(5)-methylimidazole (4(5)-MeIm), 2-phenylimidazole (2-PhIm) and *N*-methylimidazole (*N*-MeIm).

Results and Discussion

The solid crystalline adducts (Table 1) are stable at ambient condition, but on prolonged exposure to air the colour of 1 : 1 complexes faded gradually, however, 1 : 2 adducts remained unaffected. The adducts are highly soluble in ethanol, benzene, chloroform, acetone and DMF, but insoluble in water. Moreover, hexacoordinated adducts are insoluble in diethyl ether while the pretacoordinate species are soluble. This was utilised to separate the hexacoordinated derivatives from the pentacoordinated ones.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF ADDUCTS OF $[Ni(Cltpi)_2]^*$

Compd.	Decomp. temp. °C	μ_{eff} B.M.
$[Ni(Cltpi)_2 \cdot (1-VIm)]$	160	2.97
$[Ni(Cltpi)_2 \cdot (2-Me-1-VIm)]$	153	3.06
$[Ni(Cltpi)_2 \cdot (4(5)-MeIm)]$	157	2.86
$[Ni(Cltpi)_2 \cdot (N-MeIm)]$	217	2.82
$[Ni(Cltpi)_2 \cdot (2-PhIm)]$	189	3.12
$[Ni(Cltpi)_2 \cdot (1-VIm)_2]^a$	183	2.83
$[Ni(Cltpi)_2 \cdot (2-Me-1-VIm)_2]^b$	178	3.00
$[Ni(Cltpi)_2 \cdot (4(5)-MeIm)_2]$	186	2.81
$[Ni(Cltpi)_2 \cdot (N-MeIm)_2]^c$	212	2.73
$[Ni(Cltpi)_2 \cdot (1-PhIm)_2]$	205	3.08

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses.

^a $10Dq = 12\ 626\ cm^{-1}$; $\beta = 0.48$. ^b $10Dq = 11\ 029\ cm^{-1}$; $\beta = 0.57$.

^c $10Dq = 13\ 143\ cm^{-1}$; $\beta = 0.58$.

The electronic spectra of the chloroform solution of the 1 : 1 complexes showed intense bands around 12 600 and 21 550 cm^{-1} with a shoulder around 17 300 cm^{-1} , indicating square-pyramidal pentacoordinate nature of the NiS_4N chromophores⁶. The former two bands are therefore assigned to ${}^3B_1 \rightarrow {}^3E''$ and ${}^3B_1 \rightarrow {}^3E'''$ transitions⁷. The corresponding band position in the adducts of nickel(II) dithiophosphate with nitrogen donors were observed around 14 200 and 21 800 cm^{-1} in agreement with higher position of the dithiophosphate in the spectrochemical series compared to dithiophosphinates^{3,8}. The ligand field parameters ($10Dq$, B and β) of some NiS_4N_2 complexes calculated by using the equations given elsewhere⁹, are indicative of high metal-ligand covalency.

The room temperature magnetic moment of the complexes fall in the range of 2.82–3.12 and 2.73–3.08 B.M. respectively, usually observed for other high-spin complexes with NiS_4N and NiS_4N_2 chromophores^{3,10}. Size of the substituted donors and their basicity play significant role in adduct formation as it alters the π -acceptor capacity¹¹ of the imidazoles and the effective magnetic moment (μ_{eff}) of the complexes. For the 1 : 1 complexes of μ_{eff} values were slightly lower than the usual range observed for pentacoordinated Ni^{II} complexes, which could be due to axial distortion of a square pyramidal structure¹².

The solid state spectra of the hexacoordinate complexes show two intense bands around 13 700 and 21 600 cm^{-1} with a shoulder at the intermediate region (17 300 – 19 900 cm^{-1}). In some cases a distinct shoulder around 25 000 cm^{-1} was observed indicating strong charge-transfer band which were assigned as ${}^3p \rightarrow {}^4s$ excitation of sulphur¹³. On the otherhand, the weak shoulder can either be a spin-forbidden transition observed in several octahedral Ni^{II} complexes or a split component of ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(p)$ transition in a tetragonal field¹⁴. Attempt to record the solution spectra of 1 : 2 complexes yielded 1 : 1 species in solution; however, in the presence of excess donor, the spectral features were similar to the solid state spectra.

In the ir spectra medium strong bands around 350–370 cm^{-1} for 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 adducts were identified as ν_{Ni-S} modes while strong bands appearing around 510–530 and 650–680 cm^{-1} were due to symmetric and antisymmetric ν_{P-S} vibrations⁸. An increase in the frequency of ν_{P-S} in the adducts is to be expected, since there is less demand by the nickel atom for σ -electrons from the sulphur atoms.

This would tend to increase the bond order as well as ν_{p-s} . It can also be attributed to the increase of ionic character of Ni-S bond¹⁵. The substituted imidazoles and their complexes reveal common band in the region 1595–1500 cm^{-1} . These bands are assigned as ring stretching vibration, which is considerably raised in 2- or 4-substituted imidazole ligands in comparison to 1-substituted ones for the same alkyl group. This shifting is expected, as basicity of the ligand increases on changing the substituent position from 1 to 2. The increased size of the alkyl group also causes some shift in ν_{ring} vibration but this is not larger than those produced by change of substituent position. The weak bands observed around 450–200 cm^{-1} could be assigned to $\nu_{\text{Ni-N}}$.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Sodium salt of di(*p*-chlorophenyl)dithiophosphinic acid, [(Cldtpi)Na] was synthesised by the reported method^{2,3}.

IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 883-IR spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Shimadzu UV-240 spectrophotometer and reflectance spectra of the solids were recorded using BaSO_4 as reference. Magnetic moment was measured on a Gouy's balance using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as the calibrant. Elemental analysis were carried out at R.S.I.C., Punjab University, Chandigarh.

$[\text{Ni}(\text{Cldtpi})_2]$: A solution of nickel chloride hexahydrate (1.9 g, 8 mmol) in ethanol (50 ml) was added to a stirred solution of sodium salt of di(*p*-chlorophenyl)dithiophosphinic acid (6.38 g, 20 mmol) in the same solvent. The resulting green solid was washed with methanol, dried under reduced pressure, crystallised from ethanol and dried.

1:1 Adducts $[\text{Ni}(\text{Cldtpi})_2L]$ ($L = 1\text{-VIm}, 2\text{-Me-1-VIm}, 4(5)\text{-MeIm}, 2\text{-PhIm}$ and N-MeIm): Stoichiometric quantities of the nitrogen donors were added dropwise to a required amount of $[\text{Ni}(\text{Cldtpi})_2]$ in chloroform with constant stirring. The greenish brown solution so formed was mixed with small amount of methanol which on slow evaporation gave brown to pale green crystalline solids which were washed with methanol and crystallised from ether.

1:2 Adducts $[\text{Ni}(\text{Cldtpi})_2L_2]$: The nitrogen bases were added in stoichiometric amount to a chloroform solution of $[\text{Ni}(\text{Cldtpi})_2]$. The resulting pale green, yellow or reddish brown solid was washed with methanol, dried, washed again with ether and dried under reduced pressure.

In an alternative procedure, the 1 : 2 hexacoordinated adducts were synthesised by mixing excess reagents dropwise to the chloroform solution of 1 : 1 pentacoordinated adducts with constant stirring at 45–50°. The resulting solids were washed with ether and dried under reduced pressure.

On addition of excess imidazole bases to a chloroform solution of $[\text{Ni}(\text{Cldtpi})_2]$, hexacoordinated 1 : 6 and 1 : 3 (in case of bidentate donors) derivatives with NiN_6 chromophores could be isolated where the sulphur ligands act as anions.

References

1. R. N. MUKHERJEE, M. S. VENKATESHAN, M. D. ZINGDE and M. M. DHINGRA, *J Inorg Nucl Chem*, 1976, **38**, 689.
2. R. N. MUKHERJEE, M. S. VENKATESHAN and M. D. ZINGDE, *J Inorg Nucl Chem*, 1974, **36**, 547.
3. R. N. MUKHERJEE, P. K. GOGOI and R. RAGHUNAND, *Indian J Chem, Sect A*, 1981, **20**, 688.
4. T. HAZARIKA, Ph.D. Thesis, Dibrugarh University, 1983.
5. G. ROYCHAUDHARY and K. C. DASH, *Indian J Chem Sect A* 1979, **17**, 364.
6. P. S. SHETTY and Q. FERNANDO, *J Am Chem Soc*, 1970, **92**, 3964.
7. A. SGAMELLOTTI, C. FURLANI and F. MAGRINI, *J Inorg Nucl Chem*, 1968, **30**, 2655.
8. R. N. MUKHERJEE and M. D. ZINGDE, *Indian J Chem*, 1974, **12**, 848.
9. A. B. P. LEVER, 'Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy', Elsevier Amsterdam, 1968, p. 304.
10. E. K. BAREFIELD, D. H. BLSCH and S. M. NELSON, *Quart Rev* 1968, **22**, 457.
11. B. BAK, L. H. HANSEN-NYGAARD and J. RASTRUP-ANDERSON, *J Mol Spectrosc.*, 1958, **2**, 361.
12. L. SACCONI, *Coord. Chem Rev.*, 1972, **8**, 351.
13. C. K. JORGENSEN, *J Inorg. Nucl Chem.*, 1962, **24**, 1571; *Acta Chem Scand.*, 1963, **17**, 533.
14. A. B. P. LEVER and D. OGDEN, *J Chem Soc. (A)*, 1967, 2041.
15. S. E. LIVINGSTONE and A. E. MIKHELSON, *Inorg Chem.*, 1970, **9**, 2575.